

Static and Fatigue Behaviour of Unidirectional Composites in Compression

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ABSTRACT

Finite element analyses (FEA) were performed to determine the influence of varying the tab material (either steel or fiberglass) and the influence of Teflon inserts on the stress distribution of a compression test specimen. The fiberglass tab specimen with Teflon inserts provided the highest experimental compression strength, and failure in the middle of its gage length, as suggested by the uniform stress distribution obtained by the FEA. The life curve and residual strength diagram were generated to characterize unidirectional AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy in compression-compression fatigue. All the testing was performed using hydraulic grips, which proved to be a reliable and simple method to use.

INTRODUCTION

Few studies have been done on compression-compression fatigue behaviour of unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite. No standard test method exists for this type of test. Hydraulic grips were chosen as the test method and like all shear test methods, the gripping force creates a stress concentration at the end of the wedges (which corresponds to the end of the tabs). In consequence, the specimen fails prematurely at the end of the tabs instead of failing in the middle of the gage length. In order to reduce this stress concentration, the use of steel or fiberglass tabs and of Teflon inserts was studied by FEA and also compared with static compression test results. The specimen that behaved the best in static testing was then submitted to fatigue testing.

COMPRESSION TEST METHODS

The tests were performed on a conventional 100kN MTS tension-compression machine equipped with the hydraulic grips. To improve the traction of the wedges, they were plasma projected by an electric arc procedure so that the surfaces were made rough. The projection allows for a reduction of the gripping pressure by providing higher traction. The repeated high strain levels experienced in fatigue forced the use of clip gages rather than strain gages. The optimal grip pressure was experimentally found to be 4,500kPa. Static tests were performed at the fairly slow displacement rate of .058mm/s. The static tests were run in displacement control mode, monitored by a MTS micro console controller. Fatigue tests were performed on the same hydraulic grips and system apparatus as the static tests. Sinusoidal waveforms were employed to generate the compression-compression fatigue loads. The frequency was set at 5Hz for the first thousand cycles and then raised to 10Hz. As opposed to static tests, the fatigue tests were run in load control. Fatigue behaviour was studied at high stress levels, with peak stress varying between 75% and 95% of the static failure strength. The ratio of minimum/maximum applied stress (R) was 10.

SPECIMEN DEVELOPMENT

The geometry of the specimens (Fig. 1) was similar to the IITRI specimen [1], with a specimen gage length (L_g) of 12.7mm, a laminate thickness of 2.2mm (16 plies) and a width of 6.35mm. A longer tab length (65mm) was selected in order to reduce the grip pressure, thus lowering the stress concentration at the end of the wedges. Based upon information available in the literature, it was decided to consider fiberglass/epoxy tabs, the tab material most commonly used, and steel tabs, the tab material recommended by the ASTM D-3410 standard [1] for testing unidirectional carbon/epoxy. A steel tab having a taper angle of 25° was selected. This angle was chosen based on the results of Adams and Odom [2]. The thickness of the steel tab used was 1.47mm. The fiberglass tabs were chosen untapered because of their poor performance when tapered [2]. Untapered tabs are also easier to manufacture. The fiberglass tab was chosen to be 9 plies thick (1.75mm). Lefebvre *et al.* [3] tested 7 ply [0/90/0/90/0/90/0] and 5 ply [0/90/0/90/0] glass/epoxy tabs. They found the 7 ply tabs to give better results. Therefore, a 9-ply tab may have an even better compression behaviour. The tab thickness selected (1.75mm) is still in the same range as the one suggested by Adams and Odom [2], which used a 1.6mm thick glass-fabric epoxy. The [0/90]_n fiberglass tabs seem to be widely used, but no studies have been found on the optimization of the tab ply orientation for the testing of unidirectional carbon/epoxy in compression. Note that no grinding or special process was used to make sure that the surface of the tabs were parallel and precisely equal in thickness.

Figure 1. Typical specimen geometry, showing two possible types of tabs

Daniels and Sandhu [4] studied the stress distributions in six specimen configurations with different mounting jigs. They showed with FEA and also experimentally, that the use of Teflon inserts in the tab ends moves the stress concentration from the edge of the tab to a location inside the tab. This shift of stress concentration is beneficial since the tab can redistribute the stresses. With these inserts and the Sendeckyj-Rolfes testing jig [4], high compressive strengths were obtained and failure consistently in the gage length. Häberle and Matthews [5] experimentally found that using Teflon inserts in their specimens reduces the scatter of results caused by erratic tab delamination. They also mentioned that the use of Teflon inserts has the advantage of providing a full lateral support as opposed to the tapered tab, thus helping to prevent global specimen buckling. It was decided to verify the influence of the Teflon inserts on the stress distribution of the specimen selected in this study. The Teflon inserts were made by folding a 0.0254mm thick Teflon tape and by placing the folded end at 6.35mm in the tab starting from the beginning of the gage length (as shown in Fig. 2).

Only a quarter of the specimen was modeled because of the symmetry of the problem. Fig. 2 shows the portion of the specimen that was modeled, the different constituents, the applied loads and the imposed boundary conditions. The axes were chosen to be consistent with the available material properties. The x-axis is along the loading direction, the y-axis is transverse to the loading direction and the z-axis is the out-of-plane direction. The specimens were modeled by a 2-D analysis because it was assumed that there is no variation of stress distribution in the y or the width direction. The model consists of a 9-ply fiberglass tab, a layer of adhesive, a Teflon insert and 8 plies of unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate.

Figure 2. One-quarter of the specimen and the boundary conditions

Four-node quadrilateral isoparametric shell elements were used in the modeling of the specimen, except for the Teflon that was modeled with gap elements (Fig. 3(b) shows some gap elements). They restrain the tab elements from superimposing the carbon/epoxy laminate elements, which would be physically impossible. They also maintain a gap of 0.051mm between the tab and the laminate, this space corresponding to the thickness of the folded Teflon insert material. Fig. 3 shows the meshing and the geometry of the fiberglass tab specimen with the Teflon insert. As seen in Fig. 3 the aspect ratio of the elements was respected and the mesh was refined in the zone of stress concentration. The same mesh was used to study the effect of varying the fiberglass ply lay-up sequence in the tab. By changing the material properties of the tab elements: $[(0/90)_4/0]$, $[0/45/-45/90/0/90/-45/45/0]$ and $[0_2/(90/0)_3/0]$ lay-up sequences were studied. These models used 4,184 elements and 4,414 nodes. A specimen with fiberglass tabs having a lay-up of $[0_2/(90/0)_3/0]$ but without Teflon insert was also modeled with a mesh and a geometry similar to the model having Teflon insert so that the comparison of stress distribution can be easily performed. Finally a FE model having a 25° tapered steel tab was modeled. The model does not have Teflon insert and can be compared with the fiberglass tab modeled without Teflon insert. One goal of the stress analysis was to determine whether the tapered steel tab really reduces the stress concentration.

Figure 3. Mesh of the specimen with fiberglass tab and Teflon insert: (a) close-up location shown in Fig. 2, (b) close-up location shown in Fig. 3(a)

Orthotropic material properties were used for all the constituents even if the adhesive and the steel tabs are really isotropic. As can be seen in Table 1 by equating all the Young's moduli, the adhesive and the steel become isotropic. The material properties of Teflon are not shown in Table 1 because Teflon simulates a crack, so it does not play a structural role.

Table 1. Elastic properties of the constituent materials

	E_{xx} [GPa]	E_{zz} [GPa]	G_{xz} [GPa]	ν
AS4/3501-6	150	8.2	5.0	.3
E-glass/epoxy	39	4.8	4.8	.3
Steel	207	207	79.4	.3
Epoxy adhesive	2.2	2.2	.8	.4

The effect of a Teflon insert is shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 4(a) plots the stress in the x-direction along the top of the carbon/epoxy composite. The stress concentration for the specimen having Teflon insert is 6.35mm inside the tab (so at $x=12.7\text{mm}$), instead of being at the end of the tab as shown for the specimen without Teflon. The stress concentration of the specimen having a Teflon insert is 23% higher than without. This increase in stress concentration is caused by the crack tip stress singularity. As mentioned before, the Teflon insert has no structural or physical properties. Its goal is to simulate a crack and it is thus modeled by gap elements. The stress at the tip of the Teflon insert, from the FEA results, is at the failure load of the carbon/epoxy, even if only half of the critical load was applied in the model. Experimentally, the specimen will not fail at this load level and location because of plasticity that probably occurs at the tip of the Teflon insert. The plasticity will redistribute the load by enlarging the area of stress application. Typical steel has a Young's modulus of 207GPa which is very high compared to the 27.8GPa (E_{xx}) of the $[0_z/(90/0)_3/0]$ fiberglass tab. As shown in Fig. 4(a), there is a stress concentration for both models at the end of the tab, but the 25° taper of the steel tab did not soften the stress peak. This higher stress concentration (caused by the steel tab) will provoke a more nonuniform stress state in the specimen gage length, as shown in Fig. 4(b). Fig. 4(b) plot the stress in the x-direction but along the z-axis which is located in the middle of the gage length as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, non-tapered fiberglass tabbed specimens should result in slightly higher compression strength values than 25° tapered steel tabbed specimens.

Figure 4. X-normal stress along: (a) the top of the carbon epoxy laminate, (b) along the z-axis

The stress distributions in specimens having $[(0/90)_4/0]$, $[0_z/(90/0)_3/0]$ and $[0/45/-45/90/0/90/-45/45/0]$ fiberglass tab lay-ups showed little variation in stress concentrations. This suggests a similar failure strength for any of these lay-ups.

STATIC TEST RESULTS

Fig. 5 summarizes the compression failure strength and the modes of failure obtained for the various tabbing conditions. Only the specimens that failed somewhere in the gage length are presented in Fig. 5 and were considered in this study. No experimental difference was found between the specimens having different fiberglass tab lay-ups. This is in agreement with the FEA, where it was found that varying the lay-up sequence and orientation of the fiberglass tabs did not influence the stress distribution in the gage length of the specimen.

Figure 5. Experimental compression strengths and failure modes for various specimen tab configurations

The average compression strength of the fiberglass tab specimens with Teflon inserts (1,293MPa) was 23% higher than the tapered steel tab specimens without Teflon inserts and 17% higher than the same specimens but this time without Teflon inserts. As predicted by the FEA, the Teflon inserts reduced the stress concentrations at the tab ends and therefore produced a more uniform compressive stress field in the gage length, resulting in a higher compressive strength. This effect was also noticeable by the failure mode. The tapered steel tab specimens and the fiberglass specimens without Teflon inserts both failed twice at the tab end which indicate the presence of the stress concentration at the tab ends.

All the failure modes obtained in the static experiments imply the progression of the kink band, but resulting in different patterns. Odom and Adams [6] have identified five failure modes and they identified the branched transverse failure mode to be the optimum failure mode. From the data shown in Fig. 5, it was the only mode observed for the fiberglass tabs specimens with Teflon inserts. Fig. 6(a) shows a typical branched transverse failure. This type of failure always occurs in the center of the gage length and gives high compressive strength. Odom and Adams [6] associated this type of failure with the use of tapered steel tabs. This research showed otherwise since this failure mode happened in all 3 types of specimens tested, and particularly in the fiberglass tab specimens having Teflon inserts. The transverse failure, Fig. 6(b), which is physically similar to the branched transverse failure but without material ejection, only happened at the tab end, where there is a stress concentration. Fig. 6(b) presents the side views of a fiberglass tab specimen without Teflon inserts (upper) and a tapered steel tab specimen without Teflon inserts (lower). The branched transverse and the transverse failure mode gave respectively the highest and lowest strength.

Figure 6. (a) branched transverse failure in the middle of L_g , (b) transverse failure at the end of the tab

Häberle and Matthews [5] experimentally demonstrated that varying the specimen width did not significantly influence the test results. A specimen width of 12.7mm was also examined in this study because it makes it easier to install strain gages, it could be more stable laterally and it offers a larger area to observe the damage progression in fatigue loading. The thin specimen (6.35mm wide) obtained an average strength 24% higher than the wide one (12.7mm) and a more consistent compression strength. It was therefore decided to continue the fatigue testing using the 6.35mm wide specimens only. The lower strength values obtained by the 12.7mm wide specimen were attributed to the higher grip load needed to hold the specimen, thus increasing the stress concentration at the end of the Teflon inserts and around defects present in the material.

The static behaviour of the untapered fiberglass tabs specimen with Teflon inserts and having a width of 6.35mm is shown in Fig. 7. The back-to-back strain gage test consists of gluing two strain gages in the center of the gage length of the specimen, one on each face. The strain gages are aligned in the loading direction and should record the same deformation if the specimen is in pure compression. The stress-strain curves recorded by the two strain gages are very close to each other implying a pure compression state, *i.e.*, no buckling, bending or other phenomena until close to final failure, where the specimen becomes very unstable and finally buckles (Ref. [5] explains more about this type of test). In Fig. 7, the test was stopped immediately after the initial failure sound was heard.

Figure 7. Stress-strain curves recorded by back-to-back strain gages

FATIGUE TEST RESULTS

All the fatigue tests were done with the $[0_2/(90/0)_3/0]$ untapered fiberglass tab specimen, 6.35mm wide and with Teflon inserts, because of the good performance of this specimen under static loading. Fig. 8(a) presents the life curve of specimens tested at a minimum stress to maximum stress ratio of 10, (*e.g.* a cycle from -1200Mpa to -120MPa). The test results of this study are represented by hollow circles while the results of Grimes [7] are shown by the hollow squares. Runouts are specimens that were still alive when the test was stopped, they are represented by the symbols having arrows. From the knowledge of the authors the results of Grimes [7] are the only available data in the literature for the compression-compression life of AS4/3501-6 at R=10. Grimes [7] used a mixed-mode test method (the Atmur) and a very large test specimen (5.08cm wide). The fatigue results obtained in this study (with the hydraulic grips and the specimen with Teflon inserts) obtained low scatter and a longer life curves than Grimes [7]. Obviously the test method and the specimen configuration can greatly influence the fatigue results.

A residual strength curve (Fig. 8(b)) was obtained at 80% of the static strength corresponding to a fatigue life of $3.3E6$ cycles. The strength degradation is very low for the first $1E6$ cycles (corresponding to 90% of the normalized life) and then drops dramatically.

Figure 8. (a) Compression-compression fatigue life curve for $R=10$, (b) Residual strength curve tested at 80% of the static compression strength

The specimens tested in fatigue also failed in the gage length but with more material lost than in the static case because the damage was spread over a larger area before breaking, as shown in Fig. 9. After thousands of cycles the stress concentration present at the end of the Teflon inserts can be seen by the presence of tab damage, as shown in Fig. 10. Note that the tab ends are intact and that the specimen shown in Fig. 10 is still alive. No specimen failed at the end of the Teflon insert proving the good absorption of the stress concentration by the tabs.

Figure 9. Front view of what is left of a specimen gage length after a fatigue failure

Figure 10. Side view of half of the specimen, where the fatigue damage at the end of the Teflon inserts can clearly be seen (note that this specimen as not failed yet)

CONCLUSIONS

The hydraulic grips test method was proven reliable in both static and fatigue loading. It was also very simple, not time consuming and easy to work with.

The FEA done on the compression specimen clearly demonstrated that the stress concentration is shifted inside the tab area when a Teflon insert is used. The stress singularity caused by the Teflon

insert causes plasticity and it is restrained by the tabs that are gripped. The Teflon insert produces a uniform stress distribution in all the gage length region, as opposed to specimens without insert, which have stress concentrations near the end of the tab. The FEA and the static tests showed that lay-up orientation and sequence in the fiberglass tabs did not influence the stress distribution.

In compression static testing, the fiberglass tab specimens without Teflon inserts and the 25° tapered steel tab specimens also without Teflon inserts both showed low compressive strengths, failure modes either at the tab end or in the middle of the gage length, and a wide scatter in compression strength. On the other hand, the fiberglass tab specimen with Teflon inserts showed low scatter, repeatable failure mode and higher compressive strength. Therefore untapered fiberglass tab specimens with Teflon inserts are recommended for compression testing.

The back-to-back strain gage test showed a uniform compression mode in the specimen gage length until close to failure were the specimen fails by buckling.

The compression-compression fatigue test results are very promising giving a life much longer than the results published in the literature. The residual strength curve shows a very low degradation pattern until 90% of its expected life where it progress dramatically.

It should be emphasized that compression tests (whether in static or in fatigue) are difficult to perform and that the results presented here are very promising.

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